

ISic2965

I.Sicily inscription 2965

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

list of

magistrates

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2006.04; 2013.10.02

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance

above the theatre

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 45309

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI175412

1. ἐπὶ Φιλο-
2. κράτεος
3. ANAY Θεόδ-
4. ωρος Ἄρτ-
5. ἔμωνος
6. λογ. ²⁷λογ(ιστάς)?²⁷
7. ἐπὶ Ἄπ ἐ,λ [λιος]
8. τοῦ Ἄρτε μ [ᾶ]
9. AN Ἄρτέμ-
10. ων Ἄρτέμω-
11. νος λογ. ²⁷λογ(ιστάς)?²⁷
12. ἐ,πὶ Ἄπέλλιος
13. [ἐπὶ] Διονυσίου
14. [τοῦ Ἡ]ρακλείου
15. [— — —] ἀγαθ[ο]ς . [—]

16. [— — — — —]T H [—]

17.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645321

EDCS 71000506

PHI 175412

Bibliography

undefined, undefined 1888-. Bulletin épigraphique. *Bulletin épigraphique*. At 1959.0546 (wrongly given as no.4)

Pugliese Carratelli, G. 1956. Silloge dell' epigrafi acrensi. In Bernabó Brea, L. (eds.), *Akrai*. Catania. pp. 151-181. At no.3 ph

Orsi, P. 1931. [?]. *Il Mondo Classico*. 1: 52. At 52

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic2965. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4387807>